

Scores for Elite Gymnastics: gScores and gELOs

Monnie McGee^{*1}, Noah Alban^{†1}, Ayan Khan^{‡1}, EJ Rorem^{§1}, and Samuel Chen^{¶1}

¹Department of Statistics and Data Science, Southern Methodist University

November 1, 2024

Abstract

Comparing elite athletes between competitions is a difficult task due to differences in competition levels and meet rosters. In gymnastics, the comparison is complicated because not all gymnastics compete on all possible apparatus (4 for women and 6 for men). We present two methods of comparing elite gymnasts: the G-Score and the gELO score. The G-Score measure can be used to rank who are the best of each gender for each apparatus, or can be combined to find the best the all-around gymnast. Each athlete has a unique G-Score for each apparatus that carries over from one competition to the next for a given competitive season. Another approach borrowed from Chess is the ELO score. The gELO score consists of an adjusted score combining difficulty scores, execution scores, and penalty scores for each apparatus. Athletes get additional points for making the final round of a competition. While we apply these scores to elite gymnasts, it is possible to apply these scores in almost any sport with adjustments for scoring mechanism of the sport.

Key Words: Olympic sports, gymnastics, judging, scores, team selection

Introduction

Selection for the US Olympic teams involves not only choosing the best athletes, but also differing strategies regarding the use of specialists and the compatibility of team members.

*mmcgee@smu.edu

†nalban@smu.edu

‡ayank@smu.edu

§erorem@smu.edu

¶sachen@smu.edu

In sports such as track and field or swimming, the choice is made easier by the fact that a clock determines the fastest times, and thus the best athletes. No one can argue with the clock. For sports such as gymnastics and diving, the determination is made by a panel of judges. Thus, it is more subjective, and information about consistency of performance and specialties of athletes are included in the choice.

We aim to aid the choice of US Olympic Gymnasts by creating individual ratings for each athlete depending on their past performance. We use data from the UCONN Sports Analytics Symposium data challenge [3]. The US Olympic and Paralympic Committee provided data from all major domestic and international competitions leading up to the 2024 Paris Olympics. The data consisted of two files: data from the 2020 Olympics held in Tokyo in 2021, and data from competitions in the 2022 and 2023 seasons leading up to the Olympics. Data are available in a GitHub repository [2]. The results presented here came out of an undergraduate capstone course called “Big Data CORRAL” taught in the spring of 2024 at SMU. With the exception of Monnie McGee, the authors are all undergraduate students, two of whom graduated in May 2023. Unfortunately, the course began after the submission date for the UCONN had passed; therefore, we did not enter the competition.

The purpose of the competition was to select the best 5 US men’s and 5 US women to optimized the US teams’ chances of winning. Winning could be defined in terms of the number of gold medal, the total number of medals, or the total scores for the gymnasts. We chose to focus on the total scores.

Scoring Gymnastics

Before going forward, it is important to understand the scoring system in gymnastics. Men’s artistic gymnastics consists of 6 apparatus: the floor exercise, high bar, parallel bars, still rings, vault, and pommel horse. Women’s artistic gymnastics consists of 4 apparatus: the balance beam, floor exercise, uneven bars, and vault. A gymnast’s score for a given event is the total of a difficulty score, which starts at 0 and increases as more difficult moves and connections are added; and an execution score, which starts at 10 and decreases as an athlete makes mistakes. There is also a penalty piece, which is subtracted from the total of the D and E scores when an athlete makes goes out of bounds on the floor exercise or falls off the beam or bars, for example. Gymnasts can compete in any combination of events.

For both genders, there is also an all-around competition. To compete in the all-around competition, a gymnast must perform all 6 events for men, or, correspondingly, all 4 events for women. The All-Around (AA) competition is considered as a separate event. In most meets, the AA competition is held after a qualifying round. The 8 to 12 athletes, depending on the competition guidelines, who compete on all apparatus during the qualifying round and have the largest total scores, go on to compete in the AA final event. Scores from the qualifying round are erased; therefore, in some sense, the qualifying round and the

AA final are independent. Some athletes might score well on one apparatus during the qualifying round, but either do not compete on all apparatus or do not have one of the top total scores, go on to compete in the apparatus final. The apparatus finals take place after the AA final, and all scores from any athletes competing in the AA final are erased before the apparatus finals. Therefore, apparatus finals can be considered as independent events from both the qualifying round and from AA finals. During the qualifying rounds, teams can qualify for the team final; however, we focus only on individual All-Around or apparatus events, choosing not to consider team scores in our analysis.

The way in which gymnastics meets are scored has an impact on the data cleaning procedure. After importing the data into R, we substituted a value of 0 for any missing penalties. If a penalty is missing, it is presumed that there is no penalty; thus, the penalty is 0 and does not affect the score on the apparatus. Next, we eliminated team events. As mentioned earlier, a gymnastics meet consists of three competitions: a team competition, an all-around competition, and individual apparatus competitions. Because we are interested in obtaining scores for individuals, we eliminated scores associated with the team competition. Because team scores do not carry over into individual competition, the team event and individual events can be considered as statistically independent. Likewise, the score on each apparatus is summed to obtain an all-around score; however, the scores on each apparatus from the all-around competition are erased when individual events begin.

Exploratory data analysis gives some salient characteristics of the scores. The ridgeline plots in Figures 1a and 1b show the distribution of difficulty and execution scores for men's events, respectively. The scores used here are for all rounds of all events; therefore, they do not distinguish between qualifying rounds, All Around competitions, or individual apparatus competitions. The scores are plotted on the horizontal axis and the apparatus are labeled on the vertical axis. Difficulty and execution scores for each event for women are shown in Figures 2a and 2b. In general, both sets of scores for both genders are left-skewed, with the E-score typically having more outliers. The distribution of the penalty score is not shown.

Table 1 shows the percentage of athletes participating in each event for each gender. These are total number of events for 2021 to 2023, where the denominator is the number of rows in the data set; therefore, there are several athletes who are counted multiple times for the same event. For both men and women, vault has the largest percentage, followed by pommel horse for men and balance beam for women. Floor exercise has the smallest percentage of participants for women, while still rings has the smallest for men. Blanks in the table indicate that the apparatus is not part of the competition for a particular gender of gymnast.

Figure 1: Scores by apparatus for men. Left: Difficulty Scores on the horizontal axis. Right: Execution Scores on the horizontal axis. Apparatus on the vertical axis, from bottom to top: Floor Exercise (FX), High Bar (HB), Parallel Bars (PB), Pommel Horse (PH), Still Rings (SR), and Vault (VT).

Methods

In this section, we describe two different ways to rank gymnasts. One is called the *gScore*, and is based on how well gymnasts place in meets in which they participate. The other method is called *gELO*. It is modeled after ELO score in chess, and calculates the probable outcome of an athlete meet against other athletes [1].

The g-score

Recall that the data consist of national and international meets from the 2021 and 2023 seasons. The data for 2021 are exclusively from the Tokyo Olympics and only for women; therefore, from this point forward, we concentrate on the data from the 2022 and 2023 seasons. For these seasons, each meet has a different number of competitors and different judges. We want to rank gymnasts for each gender and apparatus, accounting for the differences in meet rosters and number of competitors. Therefore, we created a measure called *gScore* for each gymnast.

The *gScore* starts at 0 for an athlete's first meet appearance and is incremented or

Figure 2: Scores by apparatus for women. Left: Difficulty Scores on the horizontal axis. Right: Execution Scores on the horizontal axis. Apparatus on the vertical axis, from bottom to top: Balance Beam (BB), Floor Exercise (FX), Uneven Bars (UB), and Vault (VT).

decremented according to their rank placement within a competition. Gymnasts gain one point for every competitor they outpace and lose one point for every competitor that outpaces them. The gScore is cumulative over a season and resets at the end of the season. For example, suppose that a gymnast finishes 9th out of 25 for the first competition of the season. The gymnast places better than 16 competitors and places worse than 8. Because this is the first competition of the season, the gymnast's starting gScore was 0. After the event his or her gScore is $0 + 16 - 8 = 8$. In the next competition in which that gymnast competes, he or she would start with a score of 8, which would be incremented or decremented according to placement in that competition.

Note that the gScore can be negative. To create only positive gScores, we found the minimum gScore for each apparatus and added it to all scores. Thus, the minimum score is 0, and summing across the gScores for each event results in a positive score. To its advantage, the gScore ignores the numerical difficulty and execution scores for a meet. In that sense, it is agnostic to the contribution of an individual apparatus score. Instead, it rewards gymnasts for placing well in the meets in which they compete. It also rewards gymnasts for competing in lots of meets.

As noted in Figures 1a to 2b, execution scores for the vault are often larger than

Gender	BB	FX	HB	PB	PH	SR	UB	VT
Women	9.77	9.06					9.16	11.88
Men		9.64	9.30	9.36	10.11	9.07		12.66

Table 1: Percentage of athletes competing in each event between July 2021 and October 2023.

execution scores for any other event. In addition, in Table 1, we noted that the largest percentage of athletes for both genders participate in vault. Consequently, the pommel horse and vault contribute the largest percentage of all-around scores for men, and the uneven bars and vault contribute the largest percentage of all-around scores for women. This observation will be further investigated in the Results section.

gELO Score

The gELO is given by Equation 1.

$$gELO_{i,t} = gELO_{i-1,t-1} + k(s_{i,t} - E(s_t)). \quad (1)$$

where i is an index for the athlete, t is an index for a meet, $s_{i,t}$ represents the completed score on a given apparatus for athlete i in competition t , and $E(s_t)$ is the average score for all athletes in a competition. The gELO score considers all-around and individual apparatus as separate competitions.

The completed score is given by

$$.6d_i + .4e_i - p_i(1 - (d_i/100)) + 1 + .8(s_i/E(s))^7$$

The first half of the equation is the adjusted score. The second half is called the “final factor”, which is a boost for making the finals of any competition. Most gymnastics competitions consist of qualifying rounds (or preliminary rounds) and final rounds. The gymnasts with the top 8 to 10 scores from qualifying rounds go on to compete in the finals. In the finals, the scores from preliminary rounds are erased and all athletes start over. But, making the finals indicates a certain level of ability. The final factor is meant to account for that ability.

Unlike the gScore, the gELO score takes both difficulty and execution into account through the adjusted score. Here, we chose to weight the difficulty score slightly more than the execution score. These weights were not optimized in any fashion. We have also a final factor, with coefficients and exponents arbitrarily chosen. No investigation has been done to this point about the optimal exponent for the final factor. In chess, the value of k is based on the rating of the player and the number of competitions in which s/he has competed. Here, we use a constant value of k set at 32. In future iterations of these score, we will investigate the relative contributions of these factors and their impact on the gELO score.

Results

Figures 3a and 3b show the top scoring men, their country, the year, their adjusted gScore, and their overall rank according to the gScore. The rank is given within a year; therefore, ranks could change in 2022 and 2023. gScores are totaled for all events in which an athlete participated; therefore, athletes who participate in all of their respective events have the advantage. Interestingly, none of the Chinese or Japanese men appear in Figure 3a, and they are usually dominant. Also note that the rankings from year to year are quite stable for the men.

Name	Country	Year	Adjusted g_Score	Rank
Iliia KOVTUN	UKR	2023	12006	1
Iliia KOVTUN	UKR	2022	9500	1
Artur DAVTYAN	ARM	2023	9044	2
Artem DOLGOPYAT	ISR	2022	8596	2
Adem ASIL	TUR	2022	8410	3
Adem ASIL	TUR	2023	8360	3
Milad KARIMI	KAZ	2023	8242	4
Marios GEORGIOU	CYP	2022	7154	4
Jake JARMAN	GBR	2023	6902	5
Gabriel BURTANETE	ROU	2022	6880	5

(a) Top 10 Men According to gScore

Name	Country	Year	Adjusted g_Score	Rank
Masias KULSIKKO	FIN	2022	6098	1
Greta MAYER	HUN	2022	5368	2
Lilite RAZ	ISR	2022	5326	3
Lucija HRIBAR	SLO	2022	5166	4
Nazarin TEYMUROVA	AZE	2023	5034	1
Tjasa KYSELEF	SLO	2023	4984	2
Oksana CHUSOVITINA	UZB	2023	4930	3
Jessica GADIROVA	GBR	2022	4880	5
Georgia GODWIN	AUS	2023	4880	4
Aline FRIESS	FRA	2022	4560	6

(b) Top 10 Women According to gScore

Figure 3: Top 10 overall men (left) and overall women (right) with their gScore rankings.

For the women, there are no Russian, Chinese, or American women among the top scores. In addition, rankings between 2022 and 2023 are less stable for the women. There seems to be more variability in women’s gScores than in the men’s, and this is borne out by the fact that different women appear in the top scores each year.

Name	Year	Adjusted g_Score	Rank
Asher HONG	2023	5642	8
Taylor BURKHART	2022	5512	11
Brody MALONE	2022	5370	13
Cameron BOCK	2023	4302	26
Ian LASIC-ELLIS	2022	4238	21
Donnell WHITTENBURG	2023	3986	31
Frederick RICHARD	2023	3458	56
Asher HONG	2022	3422	37
Riley LOOS	2022	3368	38
Yul MOLDAUER	2023	3322	60

(a) Top 10 US Men According to gScore

Name	Year	Adjusted g_Score	Rank
Joscelyn ROBERSON	2023	4366	6
Jade CAREY	2022	3418	24
Shilese JONES	2022	3276	27
Simone BILES	2023	3234	28
Jordan CHILES	2022	3022	30
Jordan CHILES	2023	2722	42
Kayla DICELLO	2023	2550	59
Zoe MILLER	2022	2446	63
Addison FATTA	2022	2386	54
Shilese JONES	2023	2274	81

(b) Top 10 US Women According to gScore

Figure 4: Top 10 US men (left) and US women (right) with their gScore rankings.

The 2024 Olympics are over, and we know that the US men’s team won the team bronze and the US women’s team won gold. Team USA for the men consisted of Brody Malone, Asher Hong, Fred Richard, Paul Juda and Stephen Nedoroscik. Khoi Young and Shane Wiskus were traveling alternates. For the women, the team consisted of Jordan

Chiles, Hezly Rivera, Simone Biles, Sunisa Lee and Jade Carey, with Joscelyn Roberson and Leanne Wong as traveling alternates. However, none of these athletes appear in the top 10 overall scores. In fact, there are no US men in the top 6, and the only US women in the top 6 is Joscelyn Roberson. Keep in mind that we are not trying to determine the winner of the Olympics. The goal is to determine the US men's and women's teams that will optimize the probability of winning. However the choice was made, it seemed to work. The question remains, who would have been picked for the US men's and women's teams if the gScore had been used to pick them? Figures 4a and 4b show the top picks for US men and women, respectively.

For the men, Asher Hong, Brody Malone, and Fred Richard made the cut using gScore. Taylor Burkhart and Ian Lasic-Ellis did not compete in the US Olympic Trials, and Donnell Whittenberg and Yul Moldauer performed poorly in the US Olympic trials. However, Whittenberg and Moldauer both made the Olympic alternate team as non-traveling alternates. Paul Juda did 6 events in 2023 and 5 in 2022. His world ranks were 93 and 108, respectively. Stephen Nedoroscik is a pommel horse specialist, performing only that event in 2022 and 2023. Khoi Young ranked 102 in the world in 2023 and 88 in 2022. Shane Wiskus ranked 129 in the world in 2023 and 191 in the world in 2022. He did only 5 events in 2023. The gScore selected three of the five Team USA athletes.

For the women, we have 3 of 5 or 4 of 7 if you are counting alternates. Shilese Jones was injured during warm-ups of the Olympic Trials and could not compete. Kayla DiCello and Zoe Miller did not perform well enough and Addison Fatta did not compete in the trials.

Clearly, the gScore - or no score, really, can take injuries and illnesses into account. In addition, the gScore depends on the number of meets in which an athlete competes. For example, Sunisa Lee was ill during the 2022 and 2023 seasons. She did only one event in 2022 and finished 2nd in the Olympic Trials. Hezly Rivera did not compete in 2022 and 2023; however, she competed in the Olympic Trials and won a place on the team. Dividing the gScore by the number of meets in which an athlete competed might help mitigate the effect of increasing the gscore by performing in a large number of meets.

Apparatus Results

Figures 5a and 5b show the mean percentage score that each apparatus makes up of the total score for all around events for men and women, respectively. For men, the pommel horse score tends to make up the largest percentage of all around scores, followed by the vault. Moral of the story - if you are going to have a specialist on your team, make sure that specialist is a pommel horse specialist.

For the women, uneven bars and vault make up the largest percentage of results, although it varies with athlete. However, recall that apparatus scores are totaled, essentially assuming that the weights are equal for each apparatus. In theory, one could make up for a poor score on one event by nailing another event.

The fact that one or more apparatus contributes the largest percentage of the total score is somewhat perplexing. In fact, 13 of the top 15 gScores are from vault apparatus (not shown), which means this performance on this event will be more impactful on a gymnast’s overall gScore than the rest. The uneven contribution of apparatus to total scores will come into play when we develop a ranking system for gymnasts.

Figure 5: Mean percentage of total scores contributed to the all-around score for men (left) and women (right) in 2021, 2022, and 2023. We did not have access to data for men in 2021.

To account for apparatus impact, we can normalize the scores so that the largest total score equals 1 and the smallest equals 0. The top total gScore overall athletes is set to 1, and the worst gScores set to 0. Scores in the middle were adjusted accordingly using Equation 2

$$gScore_{norm,i} = \frac{x_i - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \quad (2)$$

where x_i indexes the total gScore for athlete i .

Figure 6 shows the US men’s and women’s normalized gScores in descending order. The results are similar as they were for the unnormalized scores, except now Brody Malone becomes the top US gymnast for men, and Simone Biles moves to third for the women. Jade Carey moves from second to fourth. Regardless, the gScore would have chosen 3 of the 5 athletes, for both men’s and women’s teams. A gymnast has to be competing in prior competitions in order to make a data driven choice for future competitions; therefore, late-comers would not be captured using a data-driven score. This shows that competitions such as the US Olympic trials are still an important piece of choosing the Olympic team.

Results for gELO scores

Rankings for the top 5 American men and women given the gELO score are given in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Men			Women		
Malone	2022	2.17	Roberson	2023	2.02
Hong	2023	2.06	Jones	2022	1.79
Burkhart	2022	2.02	Biles	2023	1.60
Lasic-Ellis	2022	1.72	Carey	2022	1.44
Bock	2023	1.70	DiCello	2023	1.36
Whittenburg	2023	1.57	Miller	2023	1.35
Moldauer	2023	1.32	Chiles	2023	1.30
Loos	2022	1.31	Chiles	2022	1.29
Richard	2023	1.30	Jones	2023	1.20
Hong	2022	1.27	Fatta	2022	1.15

Figure 6: Top US Gymnasts by Normalized gScore. The men are on the left and the women are on the right.

Name	Elo	Apparatus	Taylor BURKHART	1603.02	FXm
Brody MALONE	2162.25	HBm	Riley LOOS	1602.24	FXm
Paul JUDA	1517.14	HBm	Donnell WHITTENBURG	1577.41	FXm
Cameron BOCK	1454.67	HBm	Ian LASIC-ELLIS	1372.15	FXm
Taylor BURKHART	1426.25	HBm	Frederick RICHARD	1367.84	FXm
Curran PHILLIPS	1425.67	HBm			
			Curran PHILLIPS	1954.65	PBm
Donnell WHITTENBURG	2009.32	SRm	Brody MALONE	1613.15	PBm
Riley LOOS	1648.09	SRm	Asher HONG	1546.76	PBm
Asher HONG	1589.35	SRm	Yul MOLDAUER	1504.24	PBm
Alex DIAB	1555.64	SRm	Donnell WHITTENBURG	1442.38	PBm
Brody MALONE	1395.48	SRm			
Stephen NEDOROSCIK	1757.19	PHm	Taylor BURKHART	1940.29	VTm
Asher HONG	1541.14	PHm	Paul JUDA	1867.39	VTm
Cameron BOCK	1522.84	PHm	Asher HONG	1748.5	VTm
Khoi YOUNG	1501.59	PHm	Khoi YOUNG	1568.77	VTm
Brody MALONE	1484.29	PHm	Kameron NELSON	1434.95	VTm

Figure 7: Top 5 gELO scores by apparatus for US men.

Name	Elo	Apparatus
Jordan CHILES	2489.84	VTw
Joscelyn ROBERSO	2022.27	VTw
Jade CAREY	1965.57	VTw
Simone BILES	1609.96	VTw
Leanne WONG	1474.95	VTw
Joscelyn ROBERSO	1740.5	FXw
Shilese JONES	1711.12	FXw
Jordan CHILES	1594.33	FXw
Simone BILES	1475.84	FXw
Jade CAREY	1366.08	FXw
Shilese JONES	1711.06	BBw
Joscelyn ROBERSO	1500.18	BBw
Simone BILES	1473.64	BBw
Skye BLAKELY	1456.49	BBw
Kayla DICELLO	1417.04	BBw
Shilese JONES	2100.38	UBw
Zoe MILLER	1723.69	UBw
Jordan CHILES	1679.1	UBw
Simone BILES	1422.36	UBw
Katelyn JONG	1398	UBw

Figure 8: Top 5 gELO scores by apparatus for US women.

The gELO score looks somewhat more realistic compared to the gScore in determining the Olympic team. Note that our alternates appear on several apparatus in this list, and the hero of the meet for the men is top in pommel horse.

Simone Biles’s score might be a reflection of the lack of meets in which she competed in the 2022 and 2023 seasons. Similarly, Sunisa Lee does not appear in this list because she competed in only one event in the 2022 season.

Discussion and Extensions

USA gymnasts have a deflated gScore relative to athletes of other nations because they do not compete in as many competitions. Because of this, the gScore should be used to compare Americans with other Americans. More care should be taken when using gScore to compare Americans to gymnasts on the world stage. Further, the level of difficulty of the competitions is not taken into account for the gScore, nor does it distinguish the contribution of difficulty scores versus execution scores. Injuries at critical times and performance variability are not taken into account. Further, regardless of previous performance, once an athlete qualifies for the US Olympic trials, the performance in the trials is paramount. Here, we did not have data on the US Championships in 2024 or the US Olympic Trials.

For the gELO score, the weights and assumptions used may not be optimal. Possible investigations include a more comprehensive expected score calculation, including a measure of consistency for each athlete. The exponent for the final factor could also be further

investigated and optimized. Finally, the recency of a competition is not taken into account. It may be that meets that are closer to the US Olympic Trials should have more weight than those that are earlier in the season.

Methodologically, the all-around and team events can be considered as compositional data. For the team competition, the sum of three athletes for each apparatus makes up the score for the team on that apparatus, and the apparatus scores are totaled to obtain the overall team score. Similarly, the individual all-around event consists of the sum of the scores for each event for each athlete. One can think of each event as making up a percentage of the total score. Because every athlete competes on all apparatus during the all-around event, the scores on the apparatus are dependent. Because all teams in the team final compete on every event, the scores for each team are dependent. There is an additional twist here - it is possible that the three athletes competing on each apparatus in the team all-around are not the same for each apparatus. We make the simplifying assumption that the athletes competing in the team all around are the same on each apparatus. Incorporating the compositional nature of gymnastics data into the determining of athlete performance or into the choice of a team could aid in determining the apparatus that contributes the most to the score, and thus inform the choice of a specialist. Further, we could consider each apparatus score as a composition of difficulty and execution scores in order to determine which score is more important for a given competition in terms of the proportion of the total score.

We present two methods, the gScore and gELO score, for ranking gymnasts internationally and within the US. The original purpose of ranking the gymnasts was to choose the 5 men and 5 women that would represent the US in the Paris 2024 Olympics. Both of our scores were able to select 3 of the 5 men and women, and the gELO score included additional information about the performance of athletes on individual apparatus. However, to have a data driven method of choosing athletes, one must have data on those athletes. Some athletes did not compete due to illness or injury; therefore, their data was not available for analysis. Similarly, athletes who would have been chosen for the Olympics based strictly on the available data were unable to compete in the Olympic Trials due to injury. A combined method considering past performance with a final competition might offer some advantages over considering only the results of the US Olympic Trials in choosing the US Olympic team.

References

- [1] Statistical Analysis of the Elo Rating System in Chess — CHANCE — chance.amstat.org. <https://chance.amstat.org/2020/09/chess/>. [Accessed 31-10-2024].
- [2] CT Statistical Science Data Lab. Gymnastics data github repository. <https://github.com/ucsas/gym2024data/tree/main>, 2023.

- [3] CT Statistical Science Data Lab. UCONN sports analytics conference data challenge. <https://statds.org/events/ucsas2024/challenge.html>, October 2023.